

TRANSFORMING OPEN RESPONSIBLE RESEARCH AND INNOVATION THROUGH CHARM - TORCH

DELIVERABLE D10.2 – TORCH: COMMUNICATION MATERIALS

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TORCH: COMMUNICATION MATERIALS – ABSTRACT

Deliverable D4.1 'Communication Materials' comprises different materials to be used throughout TORCH's Project life cycle, including branding items (logos), visual identity documents (internal templates, standard presentations, and deliverables models), printed-based materials (leaflets, brochures, etc.), as well as dissemination products (website, social media, newsletter) and audiovisual products (videos).

1. INTRODUCTION

This deliverable is meant to provide an overview of the communication material to be used throughout TORCH's Project life cycle. Communication materials reported here include branding (logos), visual identity documents (internal templates, standard presentations, and deliverables), printed-based materials (leaflets, brochures, factsheets, etc.), as well as dissemination products (website, social media, newsletter) and audiovisual products (engaging videos). These materials, as well as the visual identity, are developed to support the implementation of The Communication & Dissemination Strategy Plan (Deliverable D10.3, due in June 2021).

This document is structured as follows: First, the diverse visual identity materials are presented (items are listed and briefly described). Next, the Project communication related products are introduced in the same way.

2. VISUAL IDENTITY

A strong visual identity, with a distinct logo and branding style will guarantee a consistent design, which is essential for the overall recognition of the project. In this document, templates are defined to help maintain the integrity of the project through the production of high-quality materials. A consistent branding for a project exhibits the same design elements and color schemes across all media. This means that all communication material used within TORCH, as well as the website and social media, share the same or very similar design features to create a unified and recognizable brand.

This section comprises both the logos to be used in every document produced during the Project development and the document templates, which are available for all participants in the Project web-based collaborative platform (SharePoint). In addition, a Corporate Identity Manual has also been made internally available.

Logos

TORCH LOGO

After internal discussion among all partners upon several design options, TORCH logo is agreed as shown in Figure 1. This logo keeps the CHARM-EU Alliance visual features, and, at the same time, clearly identifies the Project by itself.

Figure 1. TORCH logo.

PARTNERS LOGOS

The image of all five CHARM-EU universities is to be included in all documents and templates, as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Partners logos.

ALLIANCE LOGO

The CHARM-EU Alliance visual identity is encapsulated in its logo, and represents the five partners common project (Figure 3).

Figure 3. CHARM-EU logo.

EU EMBLEM (ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS BANNER)

In addition to TORCH logo and the partners logos, any communication activity, report, or internal document displays the EU emblem and includes the following text: *“This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101017229”* (Figure 4).

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101017229.

Figure 4. EU emblem and grant acknowledgement.

Document Templates

Templates for the most relevant Project documentation have been produced by means of Microsoft Office 2021, as follows¹:

- Letterhead (Word template).
- Meeting agenda (Word template).
- Meeting minutes (Word template).
- Permission template (Word template).
- Press release (Word template).
- Attendance list (Word template).

¹ Internal templates screenshots can be found in Annex I.

- Project/WP status report (Word template).
- Presentation (PowerPoint template) (Figure 5).

Figure 5. TORCH presentation template.

The different type of deliverables to be generated within the Project are identified, being the majority of them public and confidential reports. A common template, in order to keep consistency, is created (Figure 6). Other kind of deliverables are: Open Research Data Pilot, and Open Science Community Dashboard. For these cases, given their singularity, an *ad hoc* design will be created when produced.

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DELIVERABLE **DX.X** – TORCH: **Title**

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1 **Jaimé Urcia Ballester**
R Document, report
DEM Demonstrator, pilot, prototype
DEC Websites, patent filings, videos, etc.
OTHER
ETHICS Ethics requirement
ORDP Open Research Data Pilot
DATA **data** sets, microdata, etc.

2 **Jaimé Urcia Ballester**
PU Public
CO Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)
EU-RES Classified Information: RESTREINT UE (Commission Decision 2005/444/EC)
EU-COIN Classified Information: CNF-IDENTIEL UE (Commission Decision 2005/444/EC)
EU-SEC Classified Information: SECRET UE (Commission Decision 2005/444/EC)

Figure 6. TORCH report template (cover).

2. PROJECT COMMUNICATION

Dissemination and engaging actions will be defined in Deliverable D10.3 (Communication & Dissemination Strategy Plan). This section shows a brief description of the communication tools and materials available since the first stages of the Project, including TORCH website, social media channels and newsletter, printed-based products, and audiovisual materials (to be produced in subsequent stages).

Website, Social Media, Newsletter

WEB

TORCH website, as presented in deliverable D10.1, can be found at <https://www.charm-eu.eu/torch> (Figure 7).

Figure 7. TORCH website home.

TWITTER

TORCH Twitter account is: @torch_eu (Figure 8), and will be fed regularly with project updates, meetings and public events attended, as well as relevant news and dissemination initiatives.

Figure 8. TORCH Twitter.

NEWSLETTER

The Project newsletter is published quarterly, with relevant project news, updates from the diverse Work Packages progress and achievements, and will be used regularly to disseminate the latest results. The first issue is planned for May 2021.

Printed-based Materials

The Project leaflet and brochures contain key messages for different stakeholders, namely a brief summary of the Project and its main objectives, as well as information on the Alliance members and contact information. These items are available at the Project shared space in pdf format (printed versions will be available upon request), and will be handed out at relevant events throughout the Project, and widely distributed at public dissemination events to interested parties.

Audiovisual Materials

Short engaging videos will be produced during the first stages of the Project, in order to introduce key aspects of the research dimension of each one of the universities, with a focus on TORCH's Knowledge Thematic Areas: Food, Water, Life & Health; Biodiversity, Environment, Climate Change; (In)Equality, Economic Growth, Governance, as well as on our Cross-Cutting Principles (Transdisciplinarity and Interculturality; Responsible Research and Innovation, Open Science). These videos will be produced in each one of the languages of the Alliance members, and translated to English (in order to appeal both to local and international audiences).

ANNEX I

Internal communication templates

Letterhead

TORCH - XXX Meeting
Day, Date, Time

(Participants (when applicable))
(Concept Note (when applicable))

Programme

1.	15:30-15:45	Item (Person, Role, Affiliation)
2.	15:45-16:00	Item (Person, Role, Affiliation)
		- Sub-Item
		- Sub-Item
3.	11:00-12:00	Q&A (All)

Meeting Agenda

TORCH - XXX Meeting Minutes
Day, Date, Time

Agenda

1.	15:30-15:45	Item (Person, Role, Affiliation)
2.	15:45-16:00	Item (Person, Role, Affiliation)
		- Sub-Item
		- Sub-Item
3.	11:50-12:00	Q&A (All)

Attendees

Surname, Name (Affiliation)	Surname, Name (Affiliation)
Surname, Name (Affiliation)	Surname, Name (Affiliation)
Surname, Name (Affiliation)	Surname, Name (Affiliation)
Surname, Name (Affiliation)	Surname, Name (Affiliation)
Surname, Name (Affiliation)	Surname, Name (Affiliation)

Debrief
(Session development)

Main Conclusions
(conclusion and next steps)

Meeting Minutes

Declaration of consent: photographs, videos or other images (not paid)

Forename and surname of portrayed person	
Position / Institution	
Address	
Town / Country	
Phone number	
E-mail	
Portrayed for:	
Photo / Film / Video	
Project / Campaign	

Hereinafter referred to as 'the portrayed person'.

DECLARES AS FOLLOWS:

- The portrayed person gives permission to use and publicize or cause to be used and publicized and to reproduce one or more images (photo/video/film) of the portrayed person.
- The University of Barcelona is entitled to publicize and reproduce the images made for it, in any form whatsoever, without further permission from the portrayed person.
- The consent is given for an indefinite period. The consent also applies for the period after the publication.
- The use may include, but is not limited to, editing, duplication, licensing, distribution and incorporation in other works, in whatever form (e.g. hard copy or electronic), including posters, publications, social media, web sites, films or videos, other events and their unrestricted use, without any obligation on the part of the University of Barcelona and the CHARM-EU Alliance to seek any further authorization by the portrayed person.
- The University of Barcelona, responsible for the above-mentioned publications is not liable for third parties using the content of the stated website for other purposes without the knowledge of the University of Barcelona, that in particular also by downloading or copying photos.
- The portrayed person will not receive a fee for the use of his/her portrait by the University of Barcelona.
- The University of Barcelona warrants that rights to the photos posted on the internet will not be sold, assigned etc. without the consent of the portrayed person.
- Spanish law is applicable to this declaration. All disputes arising from this declaration will be submitted to the competent district court in Barcelona.

Signed at _____ on _____ (day/month/year).

Portrayed person
Name: _____
Signature: _____

Permission Template

